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Superconducting properties of thin film $\text{Nb}_{1-x}\text{Ti}_x\text{N}$ studied via the NMR of implanted ^8Li

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Abstract

We report measurements of the normal-state and superconducting properties of thin-film $\text{Nb}_{1-x}\text{Ti}_x\text{N}$ using ^8Li β -detected nuclear magnetic resonance (β -NMR). In these experiments, radioactive $^8\text{Li}^+$ probes were implanted ~ 21 nm below the surface of a $\text{Nb}_{0.75}\text{Ti}_{0.25}\text{N}$ (91 nm) film in $\text{Nb}_{0.75}\text{Ti}_{0.25}\text{N}$ (91 nm)/AlN (4 nm)/Nb and its NMR response recorded (via ^8Li 's β -emissions) between 4.6 K and 270 K in a 4.1 T field applied normal to its surface. Resonance measurements reveal wide, symmetric lineshapes at all temperatures, with significant additional broadening below the film's superconducting transition temperature $T_c(0\text{T}) = 15.4(7)$ K due to vortex lattice formation. Fits to a broadening model find a magnetic penetration depth $\lambda(0\text{K}) = 180.57(30)$ nm and upper critical field $B_{c2}(0\text{K}) = 18(4)$ T, consistent with literature estimates. Spin-lattice relaxation (SLR) measurements find a Korringa response at low temperatures, with dynamic (i.e. thermally activated) contributions dominating above ~ 100 K. Below T_c , we observe a small Hebel–Slichter coherence peak characterized by a

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superconducting energy gap $\Delta(0\text{K}) = 2.60(12)\text{ meV}$ and modest Dynes-like broadening. Our measurements suggest a gap ratio $2\Delta(0\text{K})/k_{\text{B}}T_{\text{c}}(0\text{T}) = 3.92(25)$, consistent with strong-coupling behavior. Sources for the dynamic high- T relaxation are suggested.

Supplementary material for this article is available [online](#)

Keywords: NbTiN thin film, superconductor-insulator-superconductor (SIS), superconducting energy gap, penetration depth, coherence peak, critical temperature, upper critical field

1. Introduction

$\text{Nb}_{1-x}\text{Ti}_x\text{N}$ is a ternary alloy with a cubic $B1$ (rocksalt) crystal structure (see figure 1), derived from Group IV and Group V transition metal nitrides [1, 2]. It forms a fully miscible, quasi-binary solid solution with its end members TiN and NbN over the entire $0 \leq x \leq 1$ composition range [3, 4], with structural details that closely follow Vegard's law [5, 6]. Similar to its end members, the alloy is a type-II superconductor with a relatively high critical temperature T_{c} (up to 17 K [7, 8]). Thanks to the alloy's facile synthesis in the form of thin films [1, 9–11], $\text{Nb}_{1-x}\text{Ti}_x\text{N}$ finds use in numerous technical applications that employ superconducting coatings (e.g. tunnel junctions [12, 13], THz receivers [14, 15] and mixers [16, 17], etc). In particular, the alloy has emerged as a promising candidate [18] for coating conventional Nb superconducting radio frequency (SRF) cavities — common components of modern particle accelerators [19] — which we consider in detail below.

SRF cavities accelerate charged particle beams via the electric fields created under resonant radio frequency (RF) excitation. Essential for maintaining a high quality factor Q_0 is low electrical resistivity of the cavity material, making superconductors like Nb ideal [19]. The performance of Nb cavities is ultimately limited by the element's so-called superheating field $B_{\text{sh}} \approx 240\text{ mT}$ [20, 21], beyond which vortex penetration occurs and resistive losses cause Q_0 to plummet. To address this limitation, coatings with superconductors having higher T_{c} and B_{sh} than Nb (e.g. Nb_3Sn , $\text{Nb}_{1-x}\text{Ti}_x\text{N}$) have been proposed [22–24]. Such coatings (with or without an insulating 'buffer' layer) are predicted [22–26] to allow such devices to operate in field regimes beyond the capabilities of 'bare' Nb cavities, a claim supported by recent experiments [21, 27–31]. Central to modelling the *macroscopic* behavior of these heterostructures, however, is knowledge of the coating film's *microscopic* superconducting properties, which are not well-established for $\text{Nb}_{1-x}\text{Ti}_x\text{N}$.

Part of the uncertainty in $\text{Nb}_{1-x}\text{Ti}_x\text{N}$'s intrinsic properties stems from their compositional 'tunability', with a transition temperature T_{c} that can be tuned with stoichiometry. For instance, a $T_{\text{c}} \approx 17\text{ K}$ has been reported for $x = 0.34$ [32, 33], while a slightly lower value of $\sim 15\text{ K}$ is observed for $x \lesssim 0.5$ [1, 2, 34, 35]. As $x \rightarrow 1$, T_{c} decreases further to approximately 4 K [34, 36]. This trend may be attributed to the properties of the end-member compositions, where NbN

exhibits $T_{\text{c}} \gtrsim 16\text{ K}$ [37, 38], while TiN has a significantly lower $T_{\text{c}} \approx 4\text{ K}$ [39, 40]. Less well characterized is how stoichiometry affects its other superconducting properties. For example, measurements indicate a magnetic penetration depth $\lambda \gtrsim 150\text{ nm}$ [17, 29, 34, 41–44] for $x \leq 0.46$, a Ginzburg–Landau (GL) coherence length $\xi_{\text{GL}} \approx 4\text{ nm}$ [4, 11, 45, 46], a lower critical field $B_{\text{c1}} \approx 30\text{ mT}$ [35, 47, 48], and an upper critical field $B_{\text{c2}} \gtrsim 15\text{ T}$ [1, 4, 9, 36, 45, 49, 50]. Similarly, the alloy's superconducting energy gap Δ is also known to vary with x , with gap ratios $2\Delta(0\text{K})/k_{\text{B}}T_{\text{c}}(0\text{T})$ ranging from 3.53 to 5 [12–17, 42, 44, 51–53]. This complexity can be further compounded by their variability with other factors such as film thickness, substrate material, and post-deposition annealing [3, 10, 11, 54–57].

As $\text{Nb}_{1-x}\text{Ti}_x\text{N}$ films are most important for technical applications — particularly in form of superconductor-insulator-superconductor (SIS) structures (e.g. $\text{Nb}_{1-x}\text{Ti}_x\text{N}/\text{AlN}/\text{Nb}$), which are widely used in tunnel junctions, THz mixers, and SRF cavities — we focus our attention on this material class. One means of elucidating its properties is through the study of the superconductor's internal magnetic field distribution $p(B)$ in the vortex state [58, 59]. Techniques such as nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) [60, 61] and muon spin rotation (μSR) [62, 63] are effective approaches for bulk superconductors, but are less suited for thin films or layered heterostructures. On the other hand, closely related techniques based on low-energy implanted spin-probes like low-energy muon spin rotation (LE- μSR) [64, 65] and β -detected nuclear magnetic resonance (β -NMR) [66, 67] are well-suited to such a situation, enabling spatially resolved measurements at subsurface depths $\lesssim 150\text{ nm}$.

In this work, we investigate the superconducting and normal-state properties of thin film $\text{Nb}_{1-x}\text{Ti}_x\text{N}$ using ^8Li β -NMR spectroscopy [66, 67]. Specifically, we report measurements in the normal and vortex states of a $\text{Nb}_{0.75}\text{Ti}_{0.25}\text{N}(91\text{ nm})/\text{AlN}(4\text{ nm})/\text{Nb}$ heterostructure under a 4.1 T field applied normal to its surface. Resonance measurements find wide ^8Li lineshapes that (symmetrically) broaden below the film's T_{c} due to the formation of vortex field lines. Spin-lattice relaxation (SLR) data reveal distinct T -dependent behavior, with a Korringa response [69] below $\sim 100\text{ K}$ that displays a Hebel–Slichter coherence peak [70, 71] below T_{c} , and relaxation that is dominated by thermally activated fluctuations at higher- T . From an analysis of these features, we

Figure 1. Crystal structure of cubic B1 (rocksalt) $\text{Nb}_{1-x}\text{Ti}_x\text{N}$ (space group $Fm\bar{3}m$, number 225). The metal atoms Nb and Ti atoms (blue and red spheres) randomly occupy the Wyckoff 4a site, which forms an face-centred cubic (FCC) sublattice. Similarly, the N atoms (green spheres) occupy the Wyckoff 4b site, can be viewed as filling the octahedral ‘interstices’ of the FCC metal sublattice. The gray bonds highlight the octahedral coordination environment of each equilibrium position. Lattice constants a, b, c for the $x = 0.25$ stoichiometry are indicated in the inset. Created using the VESTA software package [68].

quantify the parameters governing the film’s superconducting properties and compare them against literature values. Our findings provide key insight into the superconducting behavior of $\text{Nb}_{1-x}\text{Ti}_x\text{N}$ thin films in an SIS arrangement.

2. Experiment

β -NMR [66, 67] experiments were conducted at TRIUMF’s isotope separator and accelerator (ISAC) facility in Vancouver, BC, Canada. The local spin probe ^8Li (nuclear spin $I = 2$, radioactive lifetime $\tau = 1.21$ s (half-life 848 ms), gyromagnetic ratio $\gamma_{^8\text{Li}}/(2\pi) = 6.30198(8)$ MHz T^{-1} , nuclear electric quadrupole moment $Q = +32.6$ mb, and mass $m_{^8\text{Li}} = 8.023$ u) was introduced into the sample by ion-implantation using a beam of $^8\text{Li}^+$. The incident ion beam had a typical flux of $\sim 10^6$ ions s^{-1} over a beam spot ~ 3 mm in diameter, with a beam implantation energy $E = 4.85$ keV, corresponding to a mean stopping depth $\langle z \rangle \sim 21$ nm, as calculated by the Stopping and Range of Ions in Matter (SRIM) [72] Monte Carlo code (see figure 2). Prior to implantation, the probe was spin-polarized in-flight by collinear optical pumping with circularly polarized laser light [73], achieving a polarization $p_z \approx 70\%$ [74]. All β -NMR measurements were performed in an applied field $B_0 = 4.1$ T perpendicular to the sample’s surface.

During the measurements, ^8Li ’s p_z , defined by:

$$p_z = \frac{1}{I} \text{Tr}(\rho I_z). \quad (1)$$

where I_z is the operator for the z -component of the nuclear spin and ρ is the corresponding density matrix, was monitored

Figure 2. Simulated stopping profile for 10^6 $^8\text{Li}^+$ implanted in $\text{Nb}_{0.75}\text{Ti}_{0.25}\text{N}(91 \text{ nm})/\text{AlN}(4 \text{ nm})/\text{Nb}$ at energy $E = 4.85$ keV, obtained using the SRIM Monte Carlo code [72]. The target’s layer thicknesses and material densities are indicated in the inset. The stopping profile $\rho_z(E)$ (i.e. the distribution of implantation depths z) is represented as a histogram, whose mean implantation depth $\langle z \rangle \approx 21$ nm and straggle (i.e. standard deviation) $\sigma_z \approx 11$ nm.

through its β -decay anisotropy. In this process, an electron is preferentially emitted opposite to the direction of the nuclear polarization at the time of decay. This was done using a pair of fast plastic scintillation counters positioned 180° apart with respect to each other along the beam axis [66, 75]. During the data acquisition, the handedness of the laser polarization used during optical pumping was periodically alternated to control the $^8\text{Li}^+$ beam’s helicity (i.e. positive and negative) [66], with data recorded separately for each polarization sense \pm . The four-counter method was used to form the β -decay asymmetry \mathcal{A} , which is proportional to p_z [76]:

$$\mathcal{A} \equiv \frac{r-1}{r+1} = A_0 p_z, \quad (2)$$

where

$$r \equiv \sqrt{\frac{(N_F^+ / N_B^+)}{(N_F^- / N_B^-)}},$$

N_B^\pm and N_F^\pm are the beta decay electron events recorded in the forward (F) and backward (B) detectors for the \pm polarization senses, and $A_0 \approx 0.1$ is a proportionality factor that depends on the experimental setup (e.g. detection geometry, probe β -decay properties, etc).

In this work, two types of experiments were conducted (i) resonance measurements, where the steady-state (i.e. time-integral) spin-polarization was monitored as a function of the

frequency of the small RF magnetic field B_1 , which is used to map the (static) local field distribution; and (ii) SLR measurements, where the temporal decay of p_z caused by stochastic fluctuations in the probe's local field is monitored both during and following implantation. In the former, a continuous $^8\text{Li}^+$ beam was used with the frequency of the small transverse RF field stepped slowly near ^8Li 's Larmor frequency:

$$\omega_0 = \gamma_{^8\text{Li}} B_0. \quad (3)$$

On resonance, the ^8Li spin precesses rapidly due to the RF field, resulting in a loss of the time-averaged asymmetry. Multi-frequency techniques were also used to search for small 'quadrupolar' features (see, e.g. [77, 78]). For the SLR measurement, a pulsed $^8\text{Li}^+$ beam was used with a typical duration ~ 4 s. As the initial state of the probe nuclei are *very* far from thermal equilibrium, no RF field is required to measure SLR, unlike conventional NMR. During the pulse, the polarization approaches a dynamic equilibrium value, while afterward it relaxes to ~ 0 . Notably, data acquired in this manner has a characteristic bipartite form with (statistical) error bars that are governed by Poisson statistics. This uncertainty is minimized near the pulse's trailing edge, but increases exponentially with the ^8Li lifetime afterward (see, e.g. [67]). In the present study, the typical duration of either measurement was ~ 15 min to ~ 30 min.

2.1. Sample preparation

First, flat Nb substrates were prepared by cutting fine-grain Nb stock sheets (Wah Chang Corporation) with a residual-resistivity ratio (RRR) > 150 and machining them into flat plates approximately 12 mm by 8 mm by 0.5 mm. Following machining, the samples underwent buffered chemical polishing (BCP) (see, e.g. [79]) to remove the topmost ~ 100 μm of material from the surface. Subsequently, the samples were annealed at 1400 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 5 h to relieve any remaining mechanical stresses in the metal. After annealing, an additional round of BCP was performed to remove the topmost ~ 10 μm of material from the surface, effectively eliminating any contaminants introduced during the annealing process.

The $\text{Nb}_{1-x}\text{Ti}_x\text{N}/\text{AlN}$ bilayer was deposited on a Nb substrate using thermal atomic layer deposition (ALD) in a custom-built reactor at CEA Saclay, France [80]. The AlN layer was grown using a standard process with AlCl_3 and NH_3 precursors [81], while the $\text{Nb}_{1-x}\text{Ti}_x\text{N}$ film was deposited at 450 $^\circ\text{C}$ by alternating NbN and TiN cycles. Its composition can be controlled by adjusting the number of TiN and NbN cycles [55–57]. In this work, each $\text{Nb}_{1-x}\text{Ti}_x\text{N}$ supercycle consisted of 4 ($\text{TiCl}_4 + \text{NH}_3$) cycles followed by 1 ($\text{NbCl}_5 + \text{NH}_3$) cycle, as the subsequent NbCl_5 pulse etches surface Ti in the form of volatile TiCl_4 . NH_3 was pulsed for 0.5 s, TiCl_4 for 2.5 s, and NbCl_5 for 1 s, with 10 s purges after each step. This yielded a Ti/Nb ratio of 0.25 ($x = 0.25$), confirmed by x-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) [55]. Excess nitrogen incorporated during deposition was effectively removed by high-vacuum annealing at 900 $^\circ\text{C}$ [55]. Further discussion on the annealing process, along with additional characterization, can be found in section S1 of the supplemental material [82].

The film's characteristic superconducting transition temperature T_c was determined to be ~ 15 K using a vibrating sample magnetometer (VSM). Point contact tunneling (PCT) [83, 84] measurements on a similarly prepared sample show a spatial variation in the density of states (DOS) near the Fermi level, which is encapsulated by an energy gap $\Delta = 2.49(29)$ meV and a Dynes-like [85] broadening parameter $\Gamma_D = 0.10(6)$ meV. Full characterization details, along with complementary measurements on similarly prepared samples, are presented in section S2 of the supplemental material [82].

3. Results and analysis

3.1. Resonance spectra

Typical resonance spectra in $\text{Nb}_{0.75}\text{Ti}_{0.25}\text{N}$ are presented in figure 3. At all temperatures, the lineshape consists of a single, broad resonance whose amplitude decreases with decreasing temperature. The simplicity of this spectral shape suggests that all implanted $^8\text{Li}^+$ stop in high-symmetry lattice positions where the local electric field gradient (EFG) is vanishing [86]. These sites are likely the tetrahedral interstitial positions (e.g. (1/4, 1/4, 1/4) in figure 1), which are vacant in the ideal rocksalt structure. Such a site assignment aligns with the cubic symmetry of $\text{Nb}_{1-x}\text{Ti}_x\text{N}$ (see figure 1), as well as with observations in isostructural compounds like MgO [87]. In the film's normal state, the resonance's width is approximately temperature-independent, with a full width at half maximum (FWHM) of 8.126(18) kHz. This large width is likely due to the high natural abundance of spin-active isotopes that make up the film's elemental composition (see table 1), and is consistent with values predicted from dipolar broadening by host nuclear spins for the likely interstitial or substitutional sites in an ideal, unperturbed host lattice. Below T_c , the resonance broadens substantially, with the linewidth gradually increasing by a factor ~ 2 . Such a broadening is typical of a superconductor upon formation of the vortex state's flux-line lattice (FLL) [88].

To quantify these features, the resonances were fitted using a phenomenological pseudo-Voigt (pV) function:

$$pV(\nu) = \mathcal{A}[\alpha G(\nu) + (1 - \alpha)L(\nu)], \quad (4)$$

which represents a linear combination of Gaussian (G) and Lorentzian (L) components:

$$G(\nu) \equiv \exp\left(-\frac{(\nu - \nu_0)^2}{2\sigma^2}\right),$$

$$L(\nu) \equiv \frac{\Gamma_L^2}{(\nu - \nu_0)^2 + \Gamma_L^2},$$

and it mimics features of the true Voigt function which is a convolution of the two, and provides a good description of the data. Here, \mathcal{A} is the resonance amplitude, $\alpha \in [0, 1]$ is a mixing term that defining the lineshape's Gaussian fraction, ν_0 is the resonance frequency, $\sigma = \Gamma/(2\sqrt{2}\ln 2)$ is the

Figure 3. Typical ^8Li NMR lineshapes in $\text{Nb}_{0.75}\text{Ti}_{0.25}\text{N}(91 \text{ nm})/\text{AlN}(4 \text{ nm})/\text{Nb}$, measured in an applied field $B_0 = 4.1 \text{ T}$ perpendicular to the sample's surface, at select temperatures T (indicated in the figure) above and below the film's critical temperature $T_c \approx 15 \text{ K}$. For $T > T_c$, the resonance linewidth remains roughly T -independent, but broadens by up to a factor of ~ 2 at lower temperatures. The solid black lines represent fits to the data using equation (4).

Table 1. Stable spin-active nuclei present in $\text{Nb}_{1-x}\text{Ti}_x\text{N}$. Here, n_A is the natural isotopic abundance, I is the nuclear spin, γ is the gyromagnetic ratio, and Q is the electric quadrupole moment. For comparison, properties of our β -NMR probe ^8Li are also listed. Inapplicable properties are marked by an asterisk (*).

Isotope	n_A (%)	I	$\gamma/(2\pi)$ (MHz T^{-1})	Q (mb)
^{14}N	99.58	1	3.07 771	+20.44
^{15}N	0.42	1/2	-4.31 727	*
^{47}Ti	7.44	5/2	-2.40 410	+302
^{49}Ti	5.41	7/2	-2.40 475	+247
^{93}Nb	100	9/2	10.43 956	-320
^8Li	*	2	6.30 198	+32.6

Gaussian width parameter, $\Gamma_L = \Gamma/2$ defines the Lorentzian width, and Γ denotes the line's (common) FWHM. Consistent with the qualitative description above, the T -dependence of the line's FWHM remains its most salient feature. Assuming the Lorentzian contribution to the line is systematic (i.e. 'power broadening' from the single-tone continuous wave (CW) technique described in section 2) [89], we encapsulate this broadening by σ 's T -dependence, which is shown in figure 4. Although some scatter is evident, σ remains approximately constant above T_c , but increases monotonically below the superconducting transition.

To understand this broadening, we consider the following model. In the normal conducting (nc) state, the Gaussian width

Figure 4. Temperature T dependence of the Gaussian component σ of the resonance linewidth $\text{Nb}_{0.75}\text{Ti}_{0.25}\text{N}(91 \text{ nm})/\text{AlN}(4 \text{ nm})/\text{Nb}$ in an applied field of $B_0 = 4.1 \text{ T}$ perpendicular to its surface. Note that the parameter σ is expressed as a magnetic field in units of mT. The solid red line represents a fit to the data for $T < 35 \text{ K}$ using the model given by equations (5)–(9), capturing the line broadening below the superconducting transition temperature T_c , with the T -independent (normal state) contribution highlighted as a dotted line. Measured values at temperatures up to 270 K are shown in the inset, where (apart from some small scatter) σ 's T -independence is evident.

σ can be approximated by a T -independent constant, whereas in the vortex state the measured value consists of a convolution of the superconducting (sc) and nc contributions:

$$\sigma^2 = \begin{cases} \sigma_{\text{sc}}^2 + \sigma_{\text{nc}}^2, & T < T_c, \\ \sigma_{\text{nc}}^2, & T \geq T_c. \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

In an isotropic type-II superconductor with GL parameter $\kappa \gg 1$, σ_{sc} is related to the material's effective magnetic penetration depth λ_{eff} by the expression [88, 90]:

$$\sigma_{\text{sc}}^2(T) = 0.00371 \frac{\Phi_0^2}{\lambda_{\text{eff}}^4(T)}, \quad (6)$$

where $\Phi_0 = 2.068 \times 10^{-15} \text{ Wb}$ is the magnetic flux quantum [91]. In thin-film superconductors subjected to a magnetic field normal to their surface, when the film thickness d is smaller than the material's (bulk) penetration depth λ , λ_{eff} is given by the Pearl length [92]:

$$\lambda_{\text{eff}}(T) = \frac{\lambda^2(T)}{d}, \quad (7)$$

where we account for λ 's T -dependence using the analytic approximation [93]:

$$\lambda(T) \approx \frac{\lambda(0\text{K})}{\sqrt{1 - [T/T_c(B_0)]^2}}, \quad (8)$$

Table 2. Fit parameters describing the temperature dependence of resonance linewidth's Gaussian component σ (shown in figure 4) using equations (5)–(9). Here, $d_{\text{Nb}_{0.75}\text{Ti}_{0.25}\text{N}}$ is the thickness of the $\text{Nb}_{0.75}\text{Ti}_{0.25}\text{N}$ thin film, $T_c(0\text{T})$ is the critical temperature at 0 T, $\lambda(0\text{K})$ is the penetration depth at 0 K, σ_{nc} is the Gaussian width in the nc state, B_0 is the applied magnetic field, and $B_{c2}(0\text{K})$ represents the upper critical field at 0 K. Both $d_{\text{Nb}_{0.75}\text{Ti}_{0.25}\text{N}}$ and B_0 were determined independently and fixed during fitting.

Parameter	Value	Unit	Comment
$d_{\text{Nb}_{0.75}\text{Ti}_{0.25}\text{N}}$	91	nm	Fixed (from section 2.1)
$T_c(0\text{T})$	15.4(7)	K	
$\lambda(0\text{K})$	180.57(30)	nm	
σ_{nc}	540.1(19)	μT	
B_0	4.1	T	Fixed (from section 2)
$B_{c2}(0\text{K})$	18(4)	T	

where $\lambda(0\text{K})$ is the penetration depth at 0 K and $T_c(B_0)$ accounts for the suppression of the transition temperature in an applied field [94]. We treat this suppression empirically by inverting an analytic approximation for the simplest solution to the Werthamer–Helfand–Hohenberg (WHH) [95] expression for B_{c2} [96]:

$$h^*(t) \approx 0.693 \frac{B_0}{B_{c2}(0\text{K})}, \quad (9)$$

where $B_{c2}(0\text{K})$ is the upper critical field at 0 K,

$$h^*(t) \equiv 1 - t - 0.153(1 - t)^2 - 0.152(1 - t)^4,$$

and $t \equiv T_c(B)/T_c(0\text{T})$. Further details are given in section S3 of the supplemental material [82]. We note that WHH theory has been used describe the T -dependence of B_{c2} in $\text{Nb}_{1-x}\text{Ti}_x\text{N}$ [1, 50] and related materials (e.g. NbTi [97] and Nb_3Sn [96]), implying the correctness of this choice here, where fitting our data to this expression yields $B_{c2}(0\text{K}) = 18(4)\text{T}$.

A fit of equations (5)–(9) to the $\sigma(T)$ data is shown in figure 4. In the fit, both the film thickness $d = 91\text{ nm}$ and the applied field $B_0 = 4.1\text{ T}$ were fixed to their known values (see section 2), with all other parameters left free. The fit is in good agreement with the data, with the optimal values for the free parameters summarized in table 2. At this juncture, we note the good agreement of the extracted T_c with the value identified by magnetometry measurements (see section 2.1), as well as the $\lambda(0\text{K})$ measured in other films [29]. We shall consider these results further in section 4.1.

Besides the changes to the resonance lineshape induced by the superconducting transition, we also quantified ^8Li 's NMR shift K^c in the film. Using the resonance position in single crystal MgO with $B_0 \parallel (100)$ at 295 K as a reference [87], K^c (in ppm) is obtained using the expression (see, e.g. [98]):

$$K^c = 10^6 \left(\frac{\nu_0/\zeta_0 - \nu_{\text{MgO}}/\zeta_{\text{MgO}}}{\nu_{\text{MgO}}/\zeta_{\text{MgO}}} \right), \quad (10)$$

where the factor

$$\zeta_i = 1 + \left(\frac{1}{3} - N_i \right) \chi_i \quad (11)$$

corrects for contributions from demagnetization [99], with N_i denoting the demagnetization factor and χ_i denoting the material's volume susceptibility. While details of the full calculation can be found in section S4 of the supplemental material [82], we summarize the main results below. We find that K^c varies between +15 ppm to +35 ppm over the measured T -ranges. This magnitude is typical of ^8Li in many materials [66, 67], but as is common with small NMR shifts, corrections for demagnetization are a dominant contribution (+25.4 ppm here) [100]. This range of K^c is small compared to other metals (see, e.g. [101]), suggesting weak hybridization with the ternary alloy's conduction band. We shall consider this quantity further in section 4.1.

3.2. SLR spectra

Representative time-differential SLR data at various temperatures are shown in figure 5. At low temperatures the relaxation is very slow, approaching the limit of what is measurable by ^8Li due to its radioactive lifetime [66]. As the temperature is raised, so too does the relaxation, though it remains slow compared to other cubic metals (e.g. Ag [102] and Nb [103]), but comparable to other metallic compounds where the probe's hybridization with the conduction band is weak [104–106]. Interestingly, this increase in relaxation is non-monotonic with temperature, with a local maximum observed near $\sim 140\text{ K}$. At all temperatures, the SLR is non-exponential, as might be expected for a host with an abundance of spin-active nuclei (see table 1) and three-dimensional (3D) disorder (see, e.g. [107]). We note that even in the absence of structural disorder from alloying, ^{93}Nb NMR of the end member NbN also displays non-exponential SLR [108], suggesting the behaviour may be intrinsic.

To quantify these observations, we adopt a phenomenological approach used to analyze other disordered metal-like compounds [105, 106] and fit the SLR data using a stretched exponential model. Explicitly, for an ^8Li ion implanted at time t' , the spin polarization at a later time $t > t'$ is given by:

$$R(t, t') = \exp \left(- \left[\frac{(t - t')}{T_1} \right]^\beta \right), \quad (12)$$

where $1/T_1$ is the SLR rate (i.e. the reciprocal of the signal decays to $1/e$ of its initial value) and $0 < \beta \leq 1$ is the stretching exponent. This model provides a simple yet effective fit to the data, while minimizing the number of free parameters. To further avoid overparameterization, all SLR data were fit simultaneously using equation (12) convoluted with the 4 s beam pulse and a shared $\beta = 0.216(6)$ [109]. While this approach yields an excellent fit (reduced $\chi^2 \approx 1.02$), as pointed out by others [110, 111], this choice has the caveat of imparting some temperature dependence to A_0 . We assert that this choice does

Figure 5. ^8Li SLR data at various temperatures T in $\text{Nb}_{0.75}\text{Ti}_{0.25}\text{N}(91\text{ nm})/\text{AlN}(4\text{ nm})/\text{Nb}$, measured under a perpendicular applied field of $B_0 = 4.1\text{ T}$. The shaded region indicates the duration of the $^8\text{Li}^+$ beam pulse (4 s). The data exhibit T -dependent relaxation that is non-monotonic with temperature, with a significant non-relaxing or very slow-relaxing component. The solid black lines represent fits to a stretched exponential (equation (12)) convoluted with the $^8\text{Li}^+$ beam pulse using a common stretching exponent β (described in section 3.2). The displayed data have been binned by a factor of 20 for clarity.

not impede the quantitation of $1/T_1$ [112] and that this model provides a simple, accurate fit across all measured conditions. We note that the small β indicates a very broad distribution of rates, and the relaxation could also be modeled as a sum of exponentials. However, the extra parameters required to define this relaxation lead to overparametrization. The resulting $1/T_1$ values in both normal and superconducting states are shown in figure 6.

Consistent with the above observations, the T -dependence of $1/T_1$ exhibits a rich assortment of behavior. At temperatures below $\sim 100\text{ K}$, $1/T_1$ varies linearly with T , typical of metallic systems [69]. Near the film's T_c , this linear proportionality is modified, revealing a small Hebel–Slichter coherence peak [70, 71] that decays exponentially to zero for $T \ll T_c$. Such a feature is expected for an s -wave Bardeen-Cooper-Schrieffer (BCS) superconductor, but a rare observation by ^8Li β -NMR (see, e.g. [113]). Above $\sim 100\text{ K}$, additional relaxation contributions appear superimposed on the T -linear contribution. At $\sim 140\text{ K}$, $1/T_1$ goes through a local maximum, reminiscent of a Bloembergen-Purcell-Pound (BPP) peak [114]. At higher temperature, the peak vanishes and $1/T_1$ increases exponentially, suggesting another distinct contribution to the SLR.

With these qualitative features in mind, we now consider a quantitative model to describe them. We postulate that the distinct T -dependencies of $1/T_1$ correspond to the presence of distinct relaxation mechanisms, with the measured SLR rate

Figure 6. Temperature T -dependence of the ^8Li SLR rate $1/T_1$ in $\text{Nb}_{0.75}\text{Ti}_{0.25}\text{N}(91\text{ nm})/\text{AlN}(4\text{ nm})/\text{Nb}$ at $B_0 = 4.1\text{ T}$. $1/T_1$ varies nonmonotonically with temperature, with T -linear behavior below $\sim 100\text{ K}$ that is modified by a Hebel–Slichter coherence peak below the film's T_c (see inset for a detailed view). Near $\sim 140\text{ K}$, a Bloembergen–Purcell–Pound (BPP) peak is observed, while at higher temperatures $1/T_1$ increases exponentially with increasing T . The solid red line shows the fit to equations (9) and (13)–(21) (described in section 3.2), with the individual contributions from the linear slope, BPP peak, and exponential rise shown as dotted lines. The green dash-dotted and blue dashed curves show the expected Hebel–Slichter coherence peak for fixed $\Gamma_D = 0$ and 0.1 meV , respectively, using the same fit parameters.

corresponding to their sum. We make the *ansatz* that the rate contributions can be added linearly:

$$\frac{1}{T_1} = \left(\frac{1}{T_1}\right)_e + \left(\frac{1}{T_1}\right)_{\text{BPP}} + \left(\frac{1}{T_1}\right)_{\text{exp}}, \quad (13)$$

where each $(1/T_1)_i$ term represents a specific contribution i . Here, we assign $i = e$ to relaxation due to conduction electrons, $i = \text{BPP}$ to the BPP peak, and, $i = \text{exp}$ to the exponential takeoff at high- T . We now consider the detailed form of each mechanism.

The SLR in metallic systems is governed by spin-flip scattering ‘collisions’ between conduction electrons and the probe nuclear spins. The magnitude of this contribution is proportional to the DOS at the Fermi level E_F , as well as the probe’s hybridization with the host’s conduction band, yielding a relaxation rate that varies linearly with T [69]. In BCS superconductors below T_c , the condensation of Cooper pairs along with the opening of a gap in the DOS at E_F modifies this linearity, producing a coherence peak [70, 71] just below T_c and exponential decay of $(1/T_1)_e$ to zero as $T \rightarrow 0\text{ K}$ (i.e. due to the freezing-out of all cross-gap thermal excitations). Quantitatively, this can be described by (see, e.g. [60, 115, 116]):

$$\left(\frac{1}{T_1}\right)_e = \begin{cases} mT, & T > T_c \\ mT \times \frac{2}{k_B T} \int_0^\infty f(E) [1 - f(E')] [N_s(E) N_s(E') + M_s(E) M_s(E')] dE, & T \leq T_c \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

where m is the so-called Korringa slope [69], E and $E' = E + \hbar\omega_0$ are the superconducting quasiparticle energies in their initial and final scattering states (the latter defined by the NMR probe's Larmor frequency), $f(E)$ is Fermi function:

$$f(E) = \frac{1}{\exp[E/(k_B T)] + 1}.$$

k_B is the Boltzmann constant, $N_s(E)$ denotes the superconducting DOS, and $M_s(E)$ refers to the anomalous quasiparticle density arising from the coherence factor [60, 117]. These latter two quantities can be expressed as:

$$N_s(E) = \text{Re} \left\{ (E - i\Gamma_D) / [(E - i\Gamma_D)^2 - \Delta^2]^{1/2} \right\}, \quad (15)$$

$$M_s(E) = \text{Re} \left\{ \Delta / [(E - i\Gamma_D)^2 - \Delta^2]^{1/2} \right\}, \quad (16)$$

where Δ is the superconducting energy gap [118]:

$$\Delta(T) \approx \Delta(0\text{K}) \sqrt{\cos \left[\frac{\pi}{2} \left(\frac{T}{T_c} \right)^2 \right]}, \quad (17)$$

$\Delta(0\text{K})$ is the gap's value at 0K, and Γ_D is an empirical broadening parameter (e.g. accounting for finite quasiparticle lifetimes) [85]. Additionally, the dependence of T_c under an applied magnetic field follows the same relationship as described in equation (9), and also quantifies the B_{c2} independently.

We now consider the SLR contribution from the BPP peak. Quite generally, a local maximum in the SLR rate manifests when the correlation rate τ_c^{-1} of the fluctuating interaction causing the relaxation matches the probe's Larmor frequency [see equation (3)]. Far away from this 'resonance,' the contribution to the relaxation is negligible, leaving a 'peak' that is superimposed atop the other SLR contributions. Explicitly, this contribution can be described by [114, 119]:

$$\left(\frac{1}{T_1}\right)_{\text{BPP}} = c(J_1 + 4J_2), \quad (18)$$

where c is a coupling constant proportional to the mean-squared transverse fluctuating field, and J_n is the n -quantum NMR spectral density function [119]:

$$J_n = \frac{\tau_c}{1 + (n\omega_0\tau_c)^2}. \quad (19)$$

As ω_0 is fixed in the measurements, the temperature dependence of equation (18) arises from τ_c^{-1} , which we assume follows an Arrhenius form:

$$\tau_c^{-1} = \tau_0^{-1} \exp[-E_A/(k_B T)], \quad (20)$$

where τ_0^{-1} is the attempt frequency, and E_A is the activation energy. Note that these expressions are agnostic the source of the (thermally activated) dynamics causing the relaxation 'peak.'

Finally, we consider a model for the growth of the SLR observed for $T \gtrsim 200\text{K}$. Recalling the exponential-like take-off noted above, we describe this behavior empirically using:

$$\left(\frac{1}{T_1}\right)_{\text{exp}} \approx g \exp[-E_{\text{exp}}/(k_B T)], \quad (21)$$

where g is a prefactor, E_{exp} is the activation energy. Note that the form of equation (21) is identical to equations (18)–(20) in the 'slow fluctuating' limit (i.e. when $\tau_c^{-1} \ll \omega_0$).

Combining the above models (equations (9) and (13)–(21)), we fit the $1/T_1$ vs. T data shown in figure 6. For consistency with the lineshape analysis in section 3.1, we fixed both $T_c(0\text{T})$ and $B_{c2}(0\text{K})$ at the values listed in Table 2. Similarly, we fixed Γ_D at 0.02 meV to mitigate its strong correlation with $\Delta(0\text{K})$ (i.e. the present data lacks to the precision to simultaneously identify both quantities) [120]. We note that this value small compared to what is expected from PCT (see section 2.1); however, it is consistent with the range reported by others [53, 121, 122]. This (empirical) restriction notwithstanding, our approach enables a robust description of $1/T_1$'s T -dependence across both $\text{Nb}_{1-x}\text{Ti}_x\text{N}$'s normal and superconducting states, with the resulting fit in good agreement with the data (see figure 6). Values of the extracted fit parameters are summarized in table 3. We will return to considering these results in section 4.2.

4. Discussion

The ^8Li β -NMR data presented in section 3 display a rich range of behavior. At temperatures below $\sim 100\text{K}$, the NMR response is metallic, with the most salient features occurring at or below the superconducting transition, where significant lineshape broadening coincides with a coherence peak in the SLR. At higher temperatures, the lineshape remains T -insensitive, while the SLR is dominated by additional sources of relaxation, deviating significantly from the T -linear

Table 3. Fit parameters describing the temperature dependence of the SLR rate $1/T_1$ (shown in figure 6) using equations (9) and (13)–(21). Here, $\Delta(0\text{K})$ represents the superconducting gap at 0 K, $T_c(0\text{T})$ is the critical temperature at 0 T, $\hbar\omega_0$ corresponds to the final scattering state associated with the ^8Li NMR frequency, Γ_D is the broadening parameter, m is the Korringa slope, B_0 is the applied magnetic field, $B_{c2}(0\text{K})$ is the upper critical field at 0 K, τ_0^{-1} and E_A are the Arrhenius prefactor and activation energy from equation (20), c is a coupling constant, while g and E_{exp} are the prefactor and activation energy from equation (21). The values of $\hbar\omega_0$, B_0 , $T_c(0\text{T})$ and $B_{c2}(0\text{K})$ are fixed, as the first two quantities are known independently, while the latter two are determined from resonance linewidth analysis (table 2).

Parameter	Value	Unit	Comment
$\Delta(0\text{K})$	2.60(12)	meV	
$T_c(0\text{T})$	15.4	K	Fixed (from table 2)
$\hbar\omega_0$	1.1×10^{-4}	meV	Fixed (from section 2)
Γ_D	0.02	meV	Fixed (from [53, 121, 122])
m	$12.7(6) \times 10^{-6}$	$\text{s}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$	
B_0	4.1	T	Fixed (from section 2)
$B_{c2}(0\text{K})$	18	T	Fixed (from table 2)
c	$0.50(5) \times 10^6$	s^{-2}	
τ_0^{-1}	1×10^{-12}	s^{-1}	Fixed (see section 4.2)
E_A	0.0968(14)	eV	
g	0.6	s^{-1}	Fixed (see section 4.2)
E_{exp}	0.1011(15)	eV	

Korringa response. Following this dichotomy, we divide our discussion into two parts. First, we consider the low- T metallic behavior in section 4.1, followed by the dynamics observed at higher temperatures in section 4.2.

4.1. Metallic & superconducting response

To start this section, we proceed with a discussion of the resonance lineshapes, whose salient feature is a broadening upon transition to the vortex state below T_c . From the analysis in section 3.1, we find that $\lambda(0\text{K}) = 180.57(30)$ nm for our film, in excellent agreement with a direct measurement using LE- μSR [29] and comparable to a crude estimate made for different $\text{Nb}_{1-x}\text{Ti}_x\text{N}$ stoichiometries [34]. Other studies have reported values where $\lambda \gtrsim 200$ nm [17, 41, 42, 44], suggesting that our measurement is likely closer to the alloy's *intrinsic* value (i.e. its London penetration depth $\lambda_L \sim 150$ nm [18]). While λ_L value is not well-defined, we may use it to estimate the GL parameter κ for our film via [123, 124]:

$$\kappa = \frac{2\sqrt{3}}{\pi} \frac{\lambda^2(0\text{K})}{\xi_0 \lambda_L}, \quad (22)$$

which makes use of the relationship between Φ_0 and the coherence lengths within BCS (ξ_0) and GL theory. Using the values for $\lambda(0\text{K})$ and λ_L noted above, along with $\xi_0 = 2.4(3)$ nm [46], equation (22) yields $\kappa = 100(12)$, placing our film in the extreme type-II limit. While a value on this order is typical of $\text{Nb}_{1-x}\text{Ti}_x\text{N}$, we note that it justifies our use of equation (6), which requires $\kappa \gtrsim 70$.

Similar to λ , the extracted critical temperature $T_c(0) = 15.4(7)$ K from the lineshape analysis agrees with the magnetometry measurements (see section 2.1 and section S2 of the supplemental material [82]) and range expected for our film's stoichiometry [1, 2, 34, 35]. Given $\text{Nb}_{1-x}\text{Ti}_x\text{N}$'s variability in properties, particularly with synthesis and form (see section 1), this level of agreement is encouraging. Unique to our analysis approach though, is using T_c 's suppression by B_0 to make an estimate of our film's upper critical field $B_{c2}(0\text{K})$. This value turned out to be 18(4) T, which has a high relative uncertainty ($\sim 22\%$), largely due to B_{c2} 's strong correlation with $T_c(0\text{T})$. Nonetheless, its value is consistent with the range reported by others [4, 45, 49, 50]. To further validate this estimate, we calculate the ξ_{GL} using [123]:

$$\xi_{\text{GL}}(0\text{K}) = \sqrt{\frac{\Phi_0}{2\pi B_{c2}(0\text{K})}} \quad (23)$$

which yields $\xi_{\text{GL}}(0\text{K}) = 4.3(5)$ nm, in excellent agreement with prior reports [4, 45, 46], further suggesting the reliability of our analysis approach.

We now turn our attention to the Knight shifts K^c extracted from the resonance data. As noted in section 3.1, K^c is small and positive, ranging from +15 ppm to +35 ppm over the measured temperature range. The observed shift arises from a (presumably isotropic) contact hyperfine interaction, stemming from the hybridization of $^8\text{Li}^+$'s vacant $2s$ orbital with $\text{Nb}_{1-x}\text{Ti}_x\text{N}$'s conduction band. This weak coupling is a general feature of ^8Li β -NMR and similar observations have been noted for other cubic metals (see, e.g. [101]). While this static (i.e. time-average) contribution of the contact interaction gives rise to the resonance shift, its dynamic (i.e. time-dependent) component dominates ^8Li 's low- T SLR, which we consider below.

The T -linear relaxation observed below ~ 100 K is one of the hallmarks of the metallic state probed by NMR [69, 125]. Over this temperature range, a linear fit with zero intercept yields a slope $m = 12.7(6) \times 10^{-6} \text{s}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$. This value is surprisingly small and at least an order of magnitude less than in other cubic metals (cf. [101]). From relaxation in metals, this slope may be written as [69, 125]:

$$m \equiv \frac{1}{T_1 T} = \frac{2\pi k_B}{\hbar} A^2 \rho_e(E)^2, \quad (24)$$

where \hbar is the reduced Planck constant, A is the hyperfine coupling (in units of energy), and $\rho_e(E)$ is the electronic DOS. It follows from equation (24) that two sources can contribute to a small m : a small A or a small $\rho_e(E)$ (or both). Given the metallic nature of $\text{Nb}_{1-x}\text{Ti}_x\text{N}$ [4, 47], the implication of this means that a small hyperfine coupling is the most probable source for the small m , but note that a small A is also unexpected given $\text{Nb}_{1-x}\text{Ti}_x\text{N}$'s structure (see figure 1). That is, in the rocksalt structure there are a limited number of sites for implanted $^8\text{Li}^+$ that could facilitate this (cf. the van der Waals gap in layered chalcogenides [104–106]). Noting the absence

of quadrupolar splittings to our resonance data (see figure 3), symmetry constrains the possible candidates. We suggest the most plausible interstitial position to be the Wyckoff 8c site i.e. the tetrahedral interstitial sites in the face-centred cubic (FCC) lattice, situated in the center of the sub-cubes within the alloy's unit cell (see figure 1), but note that ${}^8\text{Li}^+$ may simply be substitutional for Nb/Ti in Wyckoff site 4a. The small m is even more surprising when one considers the (intrinsic) disorder present in the film, which generally *increases* its value [126, 127].

Further insight into the film's metallic behavior can be inferred from considering K^c and m in unison. Following a so-called Korringa analysis, we compute the (dimensionless) Korringa ratio [103, 125]:

$$\mathcal{K} \equiv \frac{(K^c)^2 T_1 T}{S}, \quad (25)$$

where S is a constant specific to the NMR probe nucleus ($S \approx 1.20 \times 10^{-5}$ sK for ${}^8\text{Li}$). Using our measured value for m , along with $K^c(270\text{K}) = 14.0(13)$ ppm, we obtain $\mathcal{K} = 1.29(25)$ [128]. In the limit that the conduction electrons are non-interacting, one expects $\mathcal{K} = 1$; however, deviations from this can indicate (anti)ferromagnetic electronic correlations and are often encountered for weakly interacting systems [125] (see, e.g. [101]). Alternatively, a $\mathcal{K} > 1$ may be understood in terms of an enhancement factor η resulting from disorder [126, 127]:

$$\mathcal{K}_{\text{measured}} = \mathcal{K}\eta,$$

caused by, for example, an increased residence time of the conduction electrons at the probe's site. Assuming electronic correlations in our film are negligible, an $\eta \approx 1.3$ at 270 K is implied. While this is quite modest on the scale of (disordered) conductors, it agrees with predictions (see, e.g. the 'Warren plot' in reference [126]) based on our film's conductivity inferred from measured resistivity using four-point probe method (see section S1 of the Supplemental Material [82]). Despite the film's intrinsic disorder, the above suggests that its electronic behavior is consistent with nearly-free electrons, but close to the crossover to diffusive transport.

Having discussed the metallic SLR in the film's normal state, we now consider its modification below the superconducting transition, whose main feature is the Hebel–Slichter coherence peak [70, 71] below T_c (see the inset in figure 6). While such an observation is rare for β -NMR (see, e.g. ${}^8\text{Li}$ SLR in NbSe_2 [113]), its presence is not unexpected. For example, such a feature is also observed in the ${}^{93}\text{Nb}$ NMR of the alloy's end member NbN [108, 129]. One might anticipate that $\text{Nb}_{1-x}\text{Ti}_x\text{N}$'s intrinsic disorder may suppress such a feature, but given the alloy's modest enhancement factor η (see above), any suppression is likely minimal [130, 131]. While our data is in good qualitative agreement with the theoretical description outlined in section 3.2, it does not provide a perfect match. Notably, a rise in $1/T_1$ is observed above the onset of film's (average) T_c . Indeed, transport measurements of a similarly prepared sample on an Al_2O_3 substrate show a sharp

transition at approximately 15 K, but with a small deviation beginning earlier around ~ 16 K [55], suggesting a range of T_c values. While the relaxation model captures the most prominent T_c , the SLR data appear much more sensitive to this distribution of transition temperatures than the resonance measurements (see section 3.1). The precise reason for this is unclear; however, we remark that these deviations are small and that the SLR model does an excellent job of describing the data below the film's 'characteristic' T_c . As will be clear below, this aberration does affect our ability to quantify parameters governing the coherence peak.

Following equations (14)–(17), the magnitude of the Hebel–Slichter coherence peak is dictated primarily by two quantities: a zero-temperature gap $\Delta(0\text{K}) = 2.60(12)$ meV [132], and a Dynes [85] broadening parameter $\Gamma_D = 0.02$ meV. The extracted gap agrees with PCT measurements on similarly prepared samples (see section 2.1). In contrast, the smaller Γ_D value inferred from β -NMR differs from the PCT value of $0.10(6)$ meV, which is too large to account for the magnitude of the coherence peak (see figure 6). This discrepancy could reflect differences in each technique's spatial sensitivity [PCT is only sensitive to depths up to ~ 10 nm, but has micrometer lateral resolution; β -NMR has sensitivity to depths up to ~ 60 nm (see figure 2), but averages over lateral distances on the order of millimeters (i.e. the ${}^8\text{Li}^+$ beam's spot size)]. The β -NMR value of Γ_D agrees with the 0.015 meV to 0.02 meV range reported for $\text{Nb}_{1-x}\text{Ti}_x\text{N}$ thin-film coplanar waveguide resonators, where a Dynes broadening parameter Γ_D was required in Mattis-Bardeen [133] fits to microwave transmission measurements at 100 mK [53, 121, 122]. We note that without the broadening term (i.e. $\Gamma_D = 0$) the coherence peak is much too sharp relative to the data (see figure 6).

Using the values of Γ_D and $\Delta(0\text{K})$, the dimensionless ratio $\Gamma_D/\Delta(0\text{K}) = 7.68(34) \times 10^{-3}$ was obtained, serving as a sensitive metric for quantifying disorder within the superconducting film. This value is consistent with tunneling studies on disordered films of $\text{Nb}_{1-x}\text{Ti}_x\text{N}$'s end members NbN [134] and TiN [135], and implies small disorder in the crystal lattice. The film's room temperature resistivity of $124 \mu\Omega\text{cm}$ (see supplemental material [82] section S1) further supports this, exceeding the $>100 \mu\Omega\text{cm}$ threshold for disorder reported in reference [54]. A corresponding $\Gamma_D/\Delta(0\text{K}) = 0.040(24)$ extracted from PCT measurements, appears larger due to its higher absolute Γ_D , but still overlaps with the β -NMR result. These results suggest that Γ_D at the surface is higher compared to that in the bulk of the film. The modest peak suppression and the overall agreement with the relaxation model (equations (14) and (17)) is suggestive of s -wave symmetry of the Cooper pairs, consistent with other reports [54]. Returning to the zero-temperature gap, upon combining $\Delta(0\text{K})$ with the $T_c(0\text{T})$ determined from the resonance lineshape analysis we obtain a gap ratio $2\Delta(0\text{K})/k_B T_c(0\text{T}) = 3.92(25)$. This value aligns well with the 3.53 to 5 range reported in the literature [12–17, 42, 44, 51–53], and matches with values observed for films of similar stoichiometry [15]. This ratio is also consistent with the BCS strong-coupling limit, as well as other reports

on $\text{Nb}_{1-x}\text{Ti}_x\text{N}$ [42, 52]. Overall, our measured parameters—including $T_c(0\text{T})$, $\lambda(0\text{K})$, $B_{c2}(0\text{K})$, $\Delta(0\text{K})$, and Γ_D —show good agreement with independent measurements detailed in the supplemental material [82] and the literature reviewed in section 1.

With the alloy’s superconducting properties established, it would be interesting in the future to study how they translate into preventing magnetic-flux-nucleation in SIS heterostructures [136]. Similar ^8Li β -NMR measurements have been done on ‘bare’ and ‘baked’ Nb [137] using a purpose-built β -NMR spectrometer [138]. Such measurements would complement the findings of reference [29], but under conditions closer to those of state-of-the-art accelerator cavities [19].

4.2. High- T dynamics

Similar to section 4.1, we first discuss the ^8Li resonance at high temperatures. Above T_c , the lineshape is approximately T -independent, characterized by a field distribution width $\sigma_n = 540.1(19) \mu\text{T}$ (see figures 3 and 4). The absence of any pronounced linewidth reduction at elevated temperatures (i.e. ‘motional narrowing’ [125]) immediately rules out long-range translational dynamics as the source of the dominant SLR contributions above $\sim 100\text{K}$. While it is difficult to be conclusive about their origin, we consider some possibilities below.

To begin, we consider the BPP at $\sim 140\text{K}$ (see figure 6). The fit of this peak to the model given by equations (18)–(20) is characterized by three main terms: a coupling constant $c = 0.50(5) \times 10^6 \text{s}^{-2}$, an activation barrier $E_A = 0.0968(14) \text{eV}$, and an assumed attempt frequency $\tau_0^{-1} = 10^{12} \text{s}^{-1}$ (see table 3), the latter being comparable to optical phonon frequencies. Consistent with the absence of ‘motional narrowing,’ the small E_A is incompatible with $^8\text{Li}^+$ diffusion, which is typically characterized by a larger energy barrier (in all but the most exceptional lithium-ion conductors). This is reasonable based on $\text{Nb}_{1-x}\text{Ti}_x\text{N}$ ’s structure (see figure 1), and the (nominal) ionic valence of its atomic constituents. Thus, the kinetic process causing relaxation must be *highly localized*. We shall hold off on speculating its origin for the time being, but note that the magnitude of the coupling term c is also rather small. This is surprising given $\text{Nb}_{1-x}\text{Ti}_x\text{N}$ ’s dense spin concentration (see table 1); however, the dynamic component of the local field may have an origin distinct from the static component (cf. the ^8Li β -NMR in Bi [139]).

We now consider the monotonic increase in $1/T_1$ above $\sim 200\text{K}$, which is empirically described by an Arrhenius-like relation (i.e. equation (21)). As noted in section 3.2, equations (18)–(20) reduce to this expression in the limit that $\tau_c^{-1} \ll \omega_0$, emphasizing its similarity with the BPP peak. This SLR component is governed by an activation energy $E_{\text{exp}} = 0.1011(15) \text{eV}$ and a fixed prefactor $g = 0.6 \text{s}^{-1}$ (assigned empirically). The similarity of E_{exp} to E_A is remarkable and possibly suggests a connection between the two. Much like E_A , E_{exp} ’s magnitude is suggestive of a localized kinetic process. A closer comparison with the former’s kinetic details is, however, hampered by our ability to precisely identify g ,

which is only correct to an order-of-magnitude. This is often the case for fits in the ‘slow fluctuating’ limit, where the coupling term is inseparable from the (apparent) prefactor. A crude calculation using c ’s magnitude suggests the g is equivalent to a τ_0^{-1} on the order of $\sim 10^6 \text{s}^{-1}$, which is too low to be physical. While the kinetic process’ true prefactor remains uncertain, we may infer that the coupling term for this likely exceeds c by several orders-of-magnitude.

Having discussed the high- T relaxation details, we now consider their possible origin. The observed relaxation may plausibly arise from several distinct microscopic processes. One possibility is from annealing of damage caused by $^8\text{Li}^+$ implantation, which creates Frenkel pairs (i.e. a vacancy and an interstitial defect) that may induce local atomic rearrangements, potentially involving a site-change transition of the probe ion. Another is the implantation-induced displacement of residual nitrogen atoms, leading to the formation of molecular N_2 whose thermally activated rotational or vibrational modes could weakly couple to the ^8Li spin system. A further possibility is the annealing of Ti/Nb interstitials, whose thermally activated migration to vacant $4a$ sites is supported by similar activation energies, reflecting their comparable ionic sizes and charges. Identifying the dominant origin among these possibilities is beyond the scope of this work, and further experimental studies are required to test these ideas. Additional SLR measurements at different applied fields may help refine our parameterization of the underlying kinetic processes. Central to this may be identifying ^8Li ’s stopping site, which, for a dense spin system like $\text{Nb}_{1-x}\text{Ti}_x\text{N}$, may be accomplished by searching for avoided level-crossing resonances (ALCRs) over a wide range of applied fields (see, e.g. [140]). A recently upgraded β -NMR spectrometer at TRIUMF is well-suited for this purpose [138].

5. Conclusion

Using implanted-ion ^8Li β -NMR as a local space probe, we investigated the superconducting and normal-state properties of a $\text{Nb}_{0.75}\text{Ti}_{0.25}\text{N}(91\text{nm})/\text{AlN}(4\text{nm})/\text{Nb}$ thin film between $4.6\text{K} \leq T \leq 270\text{K}$ in a 4.1T field perpendicular to its surface. Resonance measurements revealed a broad lineshape in the normal state that (symmetrically) broadens below T_c due to FLL formation in the vortex state. From a fit to a broadening model, we find a superconducting transition temperature $T_c(0\text{T}) = 15.4(7)\text{K}$, an upper critical field $B_{c2}(0\text{K}) = 18(4)\text{T}$, and a magnetic penetration depth $\lambda(0\text{K}) = 180.57(30)\text{nm}$, in good agreement with independent measurements and estimates from the literature. SLR measurements find a metallic response at low- T with a Korringa slope $m = 12.6(6) \times 10^{-6} \text{s}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$, which is modified by below T_c by a Hebel–Slichter coherence peak characterized by a superconducting gap $\Delta(0\text{K}) = 2.60(12)\text{meV}$ and a Dynes broadening parameter $\Gamma_D = 0.02\text{meV}$. These findings yield a gap ratio $2\Delta(0\text{K})/k_B T_c(0\text{T}) = 3.92(25)$, consistent with

strong-coupling behavior for the ternary alloy. These superconducting properties measured in thin films (not accessible by conventional NMR) are relevant for technological applications. In the future, it would be interesting to test explicitly how these properties translate into preventing magnetic-flux penetration in SIS heterostructures (e.g. for SRF cavity applications).

Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available at the following URL/DOI: Use this link: <https://cmms.triumf.ca/mud/runSel.html> and then input experiment number 2265 to access the data.

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Conflict of interest

The authors have no conflicts to disclose.

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